

OPENLAB
ESEV

[Towards Free Learning?] The Case of OpenLab ESEV

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[Background and origins]

- Project of the Polytechnic Institute of Viseu's School of Education (ESE Viseu – Portugal) that aims to promote, foster and support the use of Free/Libre and Open Source Software (F/LOSS), Free file formats and more flexible copyright licenses for creative and educational purposes.

[Background and origins]

- ESEV is a public institution of higher education
- Viseu (northern-center of Portugal)
- founded in 1983 as a teacher education institution
- over 1500 students and 105 teachers
- 9 undergraduate and 13 Master's programs

OpenLab emerged in an environment characterized by...

- **the lack of knowledge of the existing Libre alternatives.**
- **work habits exclusively built around proprietary software.**

[Free Software]

- To understand the concept, you should think of “free” as in “free speech,” not as in “free beer.” (RMS)

- Freedom to run, copy, distribute, study, change and improve the software (FSF, 2011).
 - The freedom to run the program, for any purpose (freedom 0).
 - The freedom to study how the program works, and change it to make it do what you wish (freedom 1). Access to the source code is a precondition for this.
 - The freedom to redistribute copies so you can help your neighbour (freedom 2).
 - The freedom to distribute copies of your modified versions to others (freedom 3).

[Activities]

- Dec 2009
- 4 teachers (voluntary basis)
- Key areas of action:

Dissemination

Training

Support

Production

[Activities - Dissemination]

- To **present and discuss** the concepts of F/LOSS and Free Culture, emphasizing the **strategic and ethical issues** related to their use. Discussing software choices beyond cost, features or brand awareness.
 - Providing information and news about F/LOSS and Free Culture, personally and via website.
 - Sharing our experiences in national and international forums, conferences and events.
 - Organizing local events to promote the discussion and sharing of ideas, usually under relevant international events (Document Freedom Day, Day Against DRM, etc.).
 - Admin of a physical space, open to the school community, with computers running only GNU/Linux and other F/LOSS.

[Activities - Dissemination]

Presentations

Events

Website + Web 2.0

www.esev.ipv.pt/openlab

Room

[Activities - Training]

- Has been a central tenet of our activities.
- Over 50 workshops.
- **Focus:** bibliographic references management, 2D image editing, vector graphics, creative coding and coding for educational purposes, digital painting, 3D and stop-motion animation, audio editing, desktop publishing, etc.
- **Contexts:** ESEV, secondary education schools, teacher training center, FNAC, CINANIMA International Animated Film Festival, etc.
- **Software:** Zotero, Blender, GIMP, MyPaint, Scratch, Processing, Luciole, ToonLoop, Scribus, Inkscape, LibreOffice, etc.

[Activities - Training]

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www.esev.ipv.pt/openlab

MyPaint

 Audacity®

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[Activities - Support]

- To **support migration** processes and **projects** developed with Free Software.
 - Installation of Edubuntu on multiple PCs for Kindergartens.
 - Distribution of USB sticks with Live versions of Ubuntu or Edubuntu.
 - Installation of GNU/Linux and other Free Software on several students laptops.
 - EVTux compilation.
 - Renderfarm and libre 3D animation pipeline.

[Activities - Support]

EVTux

Software installation

USB pens

Edubuntu at Early Childhood

[Free/Libre Animation]

- Since 2008/2009, 36% (39) of all final projects of the Arts and Multimedia graduate program (108) are developed with F/LOSS.
- 14.8% (16) are short animation movies.

[Activities - Production]

- Production poses the biggest challenge.
 - Coding and sharing of our own tools.
 - Documentation.
 - Free/Libre 3D animation pipeline.

[Activities - Production]

Documentation

Free Software for Libre 3D Animation
Using Free Software is a statement about the world we live in and how we choose to live in it.

[SWOT analysis]

- To help us in the process of strategic planning and decision-making, we decided to try to evaluate the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) of the project. This meant asking the participants to **identify the internal and external factors that are favourable and unfavourable.**

- 35 people identified
- Online and anonymously
- 23 already contacted
- 11 categorized answers so far

[SWOT - Strengths]

Mutual Support (7)

Training (6)

Ethics (5)

Physical on-site support (5)

Know-how Competence (4)

Innovation, novelty (4)

Learning sharing reciprocity (4)

Team functioning (3)

No costs (3)

Open to community (2)

[SWOT - Weaknesses]

Low visibility (6)
Resources (5) [Space (4)]
Team functioning (4)
ESEV confined (3)
Irregular activity (2)

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[SWOT - Opportunities]

Growing interest (4) [Crisis (2)]

Partnerships (5)

Software Quality (3)

Public beyond school (3)

Schools (3)

Businesses (3)

[SWOT - Threats]

Prejudice (2)

Marketing (2)

Workflow
dependent (1)

Indifference
(5)

Ignorance
(3)

Isolation
(1)

Lack of
available
resources (4)

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[What we've learned...]

Low visibility
Indifference
Ignorance

Dissemination

Training

Training

Physical
space

Team
functioning

Irregular
activities

Support

Support

Production

Partnerships

Public beyond
school

[Why it matters...]

- "Schools should teach the value of sharing by setting an example",
- social responsibility ("Educational institutions should not allow proprietary software companies to impose their power on the rest of society and its future"),
- "the school itself gains independence from any commercial interests and it avoids vendor lock-in",
 - "students are free to study how the programs work and to learn how to adapt them for their own needs",
 - financial savings, and
 - the overall quality of several already available Free/Libre Software solutions for education.

(FSF, 2011)

[Why it matters...]

Free Software is at the technological
ideological

core

Free Culture
(Lessig, 2004)

Open Educational Resources
(UNESCO, 2012)

Free Learning
(Downes, 2011)

"flattener"
(Friedman, 2006)

optimism for the future of mankind
(Attali, 2007)

Revolutionary Wealth
(Toffler & Toffler, 2007)

Open Access
(Suber, 2012)

Networked Information Economy
(Benkler, 2006)

Economics of Mass Collaboration
(Tapscott & Williams, 2007)

[Is it Free Education if...]

- Proprietary software
- Proprietary file formats
- © All rights reserved
- Can't share
- ...

Free Software is a matter of liberty, not price. Using Free Software is a statement about the world we live in and how we choose to live in it.

[Some references...]

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